

Decentralized Incremental Federated Learning with Echo State Networks

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Abstract—Federated Echo State Networks proved their efficiency in learning low-resource collaborative settings where data is regulated privacy. In this work, we broaden the applicability of this machine learning approach to a decentralized setting, where we have a set of peers connected through a logical communication topology and cannot rely on a centralized aggregation entity. In particular, we propose Decentralized Incremental Federated Learning (DIncFed), where multiple agents collaborate to learn a readout by leveraging exact consensus strategies. Such strategies include mechanisms for collaboratively aggregating knowledge towards consensus, as well as policies for dynamically updating the communication topology. Experiments prove the efficacy and the efficiency of the proposed learning methodology against a state-of-the-art iterative competitor on multiple benchmarks characterized by different levels of statistical heterogeneity.

Index Terms—federated learning, reservoir computing, pervasive computing, decentralized learning

I. INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape of machine learning, the paradigm shift to decentralized models has become increasingly vital, particularly in the context of the cloud-edge continuum [1]. As data generation and processing become more distributed, the need for efficient and scalable solutions that operate seamlessly across this continuum becomes imperative.

Within this context, we portray a scenario where we aim to learn a task involving temporal data collected by devices dispatched through the lower end of the cloud-edge continuum. Such a scenario poses unique challenges, spanning from the difficulty arising from the need to learn from temporal data under severe resource and privacy constraints to the extreme heterogeneity of network resources. These difficulties were overcome by previous works that developed Federated Learning algorithms specifically tailored for Echo State Networks (ESNs). In particular, Federated Learning (FL) [2]

has emerged as a promising paradigm, enabling collaborative training across multiple decentralized devices while keeping raw data localized, while the inherent reservoir computing nature of ESNs [3] allows them to effectively capture temporal dependencies while maintaining low computational demands.

However, most works involving these two components focus on settings where a centralized entity is available for aggregating the knowledge acquired from the participants to the FL process. There exist scenarios where including a central entity may not be feasible for several reasons. For example, in military applications, it is often the case to have an ad-hoc network lacking a central computing node offering the resources to host a server. Furthermore, security and reliability concerns may be in order in cases where other organizations offer the computing node. For the reasons above, Decentralized Federated Learning (DFL) was proposed. This paradigm keeps all the perks of centralized FL while distributing the process among a set of peers that self-organize the connection topology and the information propagation policy within the federation.

Given the advantages shown by ESN in FL, we aim to take a step further by proposing Decentralized Incremental Federated Learning (DIncFed), a methodology that exactly decomposes the efficient learning rules of ESNs within a decentralized federation. The proposed algorithm articulates over two phases: 1) a local learning phase, where peers learn a model from their local data; 2) a consensus phase, where peers propagate exact information regarding their model to reach global consensus. We propose three consensus mechanisms, namely Distributed Sum Consensus (DSC), Peer Sampling-based Consensus (PSC) and Advanced Peer Sampling-based Consensus (APSC), which differ in terms of how the information is propagated among the peers. In our experiments, we assess our methodology in comparison with a state-of-the-art approach for DFL with ESNs [4], with a broad set of operating conditions regarding the dataset employed, the statistical heterogeneity, and the communication topology among the peers.

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II. BACKGROUND

In this section, we lay the foundations of the proposed approach and describe the current state of the art of Federated Learning with Echo State Networks (ESNs).

A. Echo State Networks

When dealing with tasks involving temporal data, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) represent the neural model of choice thanks to their capability of maintaining a hidden state and capturing dependencies over time. Such capability was further enhanced by the gating mechanisms introduced with more sophisticated architectures, such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [5] and Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) [6]. While these models turned out to be effective on a wide range of applications, they are characterized by severe limitations regarding their training efficiency. Typically, RNNs are end-to-end trainable, and adapting their parameters requires backpropagating the error signal through time by unfolding the whole input sequences. In scenarios where devices are resource-constrained, this may not be feasible due to two reasons: (1) *computational*: the amount of gradient computations and error signal propagations may be too high to handle with the available resources; (2) *memory*: to apply this learning algorithm, the whole input sequences must be kept in memory devices, which may exhibit limitations as well [7]. This problem is solved by the alternative approach provided by Reservoir Computing (RC) [8], which is characterized by neural models leveraging the activations of the recurrent layers as discrete-time dynamical systems.

In this work, we employ Echo State Networks (ESNs) [3], recurrent models composed of two main parts: (1) the recurrent hidden layer, called *reservoir*, which is kept *fixed* throughout the whole training process; (2) the *adaptive* linear output transformation, called *readout*. Furthermore, we employ Deep Echo State Networks (DeepESNs) [9], a generalization of ESNs towards deep architectures. Formally, given an input sequence $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_u}$ for $t \in \{0, 1, \dots, T\}$, a DeepESN with L hidden layers of dimensionalities N_1, \dots, N_L is regulated by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}^{(l)}(t) &= (1 - a^{(l)}) \mathbf{x}^{(l)}(t-1) \\ &\quad + a^{(l)} f \left(\mathbf{W}_{in}^{(l)} \mathbf{x}^{(l-1)}(t) + \mathbf{b}_{rec}^{(l)} + \hat{\mathbf{W}}^{(l)} \mathbf{x}^{(l)}(t-1) \right), \\ \mathbf{y}(t) &= \mathbf{W}[\mathbf{x}^{(1)}(t), \dots, \mathbf{x}^{(L)}(t)] + \mathbf{b}_{out}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The former equation models the state transition of a generic layer l , where $\mathbf{W}_{in}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l \times N_{l-1}}$ is the input-to-reservoir transformation, $\hat{\mathbf{W}}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l \times N_l}$ is the recurrent reservoir-to-reservoir transformation, $\mathbf{b}_{rec}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ is the reservoir bias and $a^{(l)} \in (0, 1]$ is the leaking rate. When $l = 1$, the input sequence of the reservoir $\mathbf{x}^{(0)}(t)$ is $\mathbf{u}(t)$, and $N_0 = N_u$. The latter equation models the readout transformation, where $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_y \times (N_1 + \dots + N_L)}$ applies a linear transformation to the concatenation of the hidden states of all layers at time t . The training efficiency of DeepESNs comes at the sole constraint of ensuring the asymptotic stability of the linearized dynamical

system. This can be done by initializing the recurrent matrices of the reservoirs such that $\max_{k=1, \dots, L} \rho(\hat{\mathbf{W}}^{(k)}) < 1$ [10]. While this represents only the necessary condition of the so-called the Echo State Property (ESP) [11], in many applications, it turns out to be sufficient to avoid the divergence of the dynamical system. Upon enforcing this condition in the initialization phase, the parameters $\mathbf{W}_{in}^{(l)}$, $\hat{\mathbf{W}}^{(l)}$, and $\mathbf{b}_{rec}^{(l)}$ are kept fixed for all $l \in \{1, \dots, L\}$. This setup, along with the linearity of the readout transformation, allows lightweight learning techniques to be employed for its adaptation. The most common approach, which we rely on in this work, is Ridge Regression (RR). It treats the optimization problem as a linear system by applying the following closed-form solution:

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{S}^T(\mathbf{S}\mathbf{S}^T + \lambda\mathbf{I})^{-1}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_y \times T}$ is the matrix of time-ordered labels, $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N_1 + \dots + N_L) \times T}$ is the matrix of time-ordered hidden states of all the reservoirs, \mathbf{I} is the identity with dimensionality per the sizes of the reservoirs, and λ is an $L2$ regularization parameter.

B. Decentralized Federated Learning

Federated Learning (FL) is a collaborative learning setting where devices share knowledge from their local learning processes without exchanging raw data. The main objective of its proposal was to achieve a privacy-compliant machine learning setting. However, avoiding data exchange makes this setting much more communication-efficient than regular distributed settings, making it a valuable tool for learning processes happening on data dislocated over the cloud-edge continuum.

In FL, the objective is to find the model that minimizes the loss function L :

$$\arg \min_f \sum_{c=1}^C p_c L_c(\mathcal{D}_c; f) \quad (3)$$

where, for each learner $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ in the federation, \mathcal{D}_c is their local dataset, L_c is the local realization of the loss function, and p_c is a weighting factor, such that $\sum_{c=1}^C p_c = 1$, which balances the contributions from the learners according to a defined policy. The most common approach to FL consists of a client-server topology of interactions among the learners. The clients perform a local learning process on the collected data, while the server acts as a centralized entity that aggregates knowledge (i.e., the *local models*) forwarded by clients. Federated Averaging (FedAvg) represents the first example of such an approach, where clients learn locally via SGD, and the server performs an average of the models trained by the client, weighted according to the sizes of their local datasets to account for statistical heterogeneity. There exist verticalizations of FL techniques leveraging the peculiarities of the architecture of ESNs. In particular, Incremental Federated Learning (IncFed) [12], [13] decomposes the closed-form solution of RR to perform a single-shot, exact aggregation of the models learned by the clients. FedIP [14] casts FedAvg to include Intrinsic Plasticity as a local update rule and allows learning from non-stationary data streams [15].

On many occasions, having a centralized entity for aggregating knowledge from participants to the learning processes may not be feasible. This happens due to multiple reasons:

- *Design choices*: in certain applications, the underlying infrastructure may not provide for the use of centralized entities (e.g., ad-hoc networks in military applications);
- *Scaling*: in a cross-device setting, the massive distribution of clients may overload the server with requests;
- *Single point of failure*: a failure of the server may lead to the failure of the entire FL process;
- *Security*: the server may be deployed on untrusted nodes.

To tackle these issues, Decentralized Federated Learning (DFL) was proposed [16]. This approach organizes the learning process among a set of peers connected via arbitrary topologies, each interleaving learning and aggregation phases. In [17], authors propose a decentralized version of FedAvg, where each peer interleaves local learning with aggregation by averaging models from neighbors in the connection topology.

To the best of our knowledge, there exists only one verticalization of DFL towards the use of ESNs. In particular, authors in [18] address the optimization of the readout of each peer by implicitly minimizing the global augmented Lagrangian Least Squares problem by applying Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM) with Distributed Average Consensus (DAC) as a consensus mechanism. A peer u first computes its local readout \mathbf{W}_u via RR. Then, it starts the consensus phase, which unfolds over T rounds, and in the t -th round a peer u 1) performs K internal iterations where it requests the local readout \mathbf{W}_v and the local parameters of the augmented lagrangian $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_v$ to every neighbor $v \in \mathcal{N}(u)$ in the connection topology; 2) computes the residuals for the error minimization.

III. DECENTRALIZED INCREMENTAL FEDERATED LEARNING WITH ECHO STATE NETWORKS

We propose Decentralized Incremental Federated Learning (DIncFed), a DFL algorithm which allows a network of peer agents to perform an exact optimization of their local ESN through an easy algebraic decomposition of the RR. The proposed algorithm (summarized in Algorithm 1) articulates in two phases: 1) Local Learning (Section III-A), where peers learn the statistics for the RR from their local dataset; 2) Consensus phase (Section III-B): for K iterations, each peer determines the neighbors with which to exchange the statistics and aggregates them to update their local readout with the closed-form solution in eq. (2). In our description, the communication topology among peers is *logical*, and defined as an undirected graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ where \mathcal{V} is the set of peers participating to the DFL process, and \mathcal{E} is the set of undirected links connecting two peers.

A. Local Learning

In the local learning phase of each peer, we can exploit a simple algebraic decomposition of RR, which allows us to distribute the computation of (2) across all the participants to the learning process without losing information [12]. In particular, given a local dataset of a peer \mathcal{D}_v , each peer

Algorithm 1 DIncFed on peer u

Input: consensus iterations K , *consensus_strategy*, L2 regularization λ

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 $\mathbf{U}_u, \mathbf{Y}_u \leftarrow \mathcal{D}_u,$ 
 $\mathbf{S}_u \leftarrow \text{reservoir}(\mathbf{U}_u)$ 
 $\mathbf{A}_u \leftarrow \mathbf{Y}_u \mathbf{S}_u^T$ 
 $\mathbf{B}_u \leftarrow \mathbf{S}_u \mathbf{S}_u^T$ 
 $\mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u \leftarrow \text{consensus\_strategy}(\mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u, K)$ 
 $\mathbf{W}_u \leftarrow \mathbf{A}_u (\mathbf{B}_u + \lambda \mathbf{I})^{-1}$ 

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preprocesses the local dataset by applying the hidden layers of the reservoir, thus producing a matrix of time-ordered hidden states $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s \times T}$, where N_s is the sum of the hidden sizes of the DeepESN $N_s = \sum_{l=1}^L N_l$. Then, each peer $v \in \mathcal{V}$ can compute the local statistics of the RR, formalized as

$$\mathbf{A}_v = \mathbf{Y}_v \mathbf{S}_v^T, \quad \mathbf{B}_v = \mathbf{S}_v \mathbf{S}_v^T, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_v \in \mathbb{R}^{N_y \times N_s}$ corresponds to the states-to-target correlation matrix (left-hand side of eq. (2)), and $\mathbf{B}_v \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s \times N_s}$ corresponds to the self-correlation matrix of the states of the DeepESN. These matrices are exchanged among peers during the consensus phase.

B. Consensus Phase

We assume that a logical communication topology $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, is initialized randomly with three approaches: 1) Random Regular (RandR), connecting each peer with k nodes randomly, where we fixed $k = 2$; 2) Newman-Watts-Strogatz (NWS) enriches the RandR initializer by adding extra links between peers with probability p , that we fixed to 0.5; 3) Barabasi-Albert (BA) weights the probability of adding new links proportionally to the current degree of each node, with 2 set as the minimum degree of each node. A peer u is connected with a set of neighboring nodes $\mathcal{N}(u) = \{v \mid (u, v), (v, u) \in \mathcal{E}, v \in \mathcal{V}\}$. Given this setup, a consensus mechanism provides for a twofold purpose: defines the neighbors with which the peer will exchange the statistics during the current iteration. Then, it defines what information is exchanged and the aggregation technique to update the local model with the received statistics. A consensus mechanism unfolds over K iterations to ensure the propagation of the local information through the network. In the following, we propose three consensus mechanisms, depicted in Figure 1, which incrementally leverage the definition of Ridge Regression in a distributed setting.

1) *Distributed Sum Consensus (DSC)*: This mechanism adapts the logic of DAC to propagate the information to reach the exact consensus with Ridge Regression (Algorithm 2). The algorithm is initialized by setting the exchangeable statistics of u , i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{A}}, \hat{\mathbf{B}}$ to the local statistics $\mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u$. During the k -th iteration, a peer u requests the statistics to all the neighboring nodes $v \in \mathcal{N}(u)$. Upon aggregation by summation, these statistics will serve two purposes. First, they will be accumulated on the current local model of u . Then,

Fig. 1. Representation of the three consensus mechanisms. We consider the depicted initial topology, and we focus on peer C . With DSC (uppermost), C broadcasts requests to all neighbors and aggregates their local models. With PSC (center), C requests the local model only to F (which already completed an iteration interacting with D), aggregates the *local* model from F and includes D to neighbors. With APSC (lowermost), C requests model to F (which already completed an iteration interacting with D), which recognizes that C did not visit D , and responds with the aggregated local model. C aggregates the received model and includes D to neighbors. Finally, APSC (lowermost) combines the two approaches by leveraging partially aggregated matrices from neighbors.

Algorithm 2 Distributed Sum Consensus on node u

Input: initial tuple $\mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u$, consensus iterations K

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 $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_u^0, \hat{\mathbf{B}}_u^0 \leftarrow \mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u$ 
for  $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$  do
   $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathcal{N}}, \hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\mathcal{N}}^k \leftarrow$  Request statistics to all  $v \in \mathcal{N}(u)$ 
   $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_u^k, \hat{\mathbf{B}}_u^k \leftarrow \sum_{v \in \mathcal{N}(u)} \hat{\mathbf{A}}_v^k, \sum_{v \in \mathcal{N}(u)} \hat{\mathbf{B}}_v^k$ 
   $\mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u \leftarrow \mathbf{A}_u + \hat{\mathbf{A}}_u^k, \mathbf{B}_u + \hat{\mathbf{B}}_u^k$ 
end for
return  $\mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u$ 

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they will replace the exchangeable statistics $\hat{\mathbf{A}}, \hat{\mathbf{B}}$, which, in the absence of loops in the connection topology, allows for avoiding information replication during the propagation. Finally, note that each iteration acts as a barrier across the federation: all the nodes must be synchronized on the k -th iteration. The main advantage of this consensus mechanism is that it requires, at most, a number of iterations K equal to the longest path of the network to reach convergence.

2) *Peer Sampling-based Consensus (PSC)*: Peer Sampling [19] is a gossip protocol used to spread information among peers by dynamically adapting the set of logical neighbors in the connection topology. We employ this protocol here by proposing PSC, summarized in Algorithm 3. In the initializa-

tion phase, a peer u sets the exchangeable statistics $\hat{\mathbf{A}}, \hat{\mathbf{B}}$ to the local statistics $\mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u$ and a register \mathcal{R} containing the addresses of peers which already provided their statistics. In the k -th iteration, a peer u samples one neighbor $v \in \mathcal{N}(u)$ with priority to the ones that are not contained in \mathcal{R} and not queried recently. Then, u requests to v the set of its neighbors $\mathcal{N}(v)$. If $v \notin \mathcal{R}$, u requests also its statistics, aggregates them to the local ones via summation and includes v in \mathcal{R} . Finally, u updates its set of neighbors $\mathcal{N}(u)$ with the ones received from v . In this mechanism, the main advantage stands in transferring the statistics only to one neighbor for each iteration, which is a significant reduction with respect to the $|\mathcal{N}(u)|$ transfers per iteration of DSC. Since the exchangeable statistics are fixed during initialization, participating peers do not require synchronization throughout the process. This mechanism converges with a number of iterations equal to $|\mathcal{V}|-1$, requiring communication to all nodes in the federation.

3) *Advanced Peer Sampling-based Consensus (APSC)*: While PSC provides significant advantages in terms of efficiency against DSC, the number of iterations to reach convergence equals the number of peers in the network, i.e., $|\mathcal{V}|$, which is not feasible for arbitrarily large networks. However, while DSC could result more effective in this sense thanks to the partial aggregations performed by all the peers, synchronizing the whole federation and broadcasting the statistics

Algorithm 3 Peer Sampling-based Consensus on node u

Input: initial tuple $\mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u$, consensus iterations K

$\hat{\mathbf{A}}_u, \hat{\mathbf{B}}_u \leftarrow \mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u$

$\mathcal{R} \leftarrow \emptyset$

for $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ **do**

$v \leftarrow \text{sample_from}(\mathcal{N}(u))$

$\mathcal{N}(v) \leftarrow \text{Request neighbors to } v$

if $v \notin \mathcal{R}$ **then**

$\hat{\mathbf{A}}_v^k, \hat{\mathbf{B}}_v^k \leftarrow \text{Request statistics to } v$

$\mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u \leftarrow \mathbf{A}_u + \hat{\mathbf{A}}_v^k, \mathbf{B}_u + \hat{\mathbf{B}}_v^k$

$\mathcal{R} \leftarrow \mathcal{R} \cup \{v\}$

$k \leftarrow k + 1$

end if

$\mathcal{N}(u) \leftarrow \text{update_neighbors}(\mathcal{N}(u), \mathcal{N}(v))$

end for

return $\mathbf{A}_u, \mathbf{B}_u$

may not be feasible as well. Thus, combine the best of both worlds by proposing APSC, an asynchronous consensus mechanism that optimizes the amount of data exchanged while leveraging partial aggregations performed by peers throughout the learning process. Starting from the same skeleton of PSC, whenever a peer u queries a neighbor v to send the local statistics, it attaches to the request the set of IDs from which u already received the matrices, i.e., \mathcal{R}_u . When receiving the request, v tests the following conditions:

- $C1$: $\mathcal{R}_u \cap (\mathcal{R}_v \setminus \{u\}) = \emptyset$, meaning that v aggregated statistics which are *unknown* from u ;
- $C2$: $|\mathcal{R}_v \setminus \{c\}| > |\mathcal{R}_u| + 1$, meaning that v aggregated *more* statistics than u .

If $C1$ holds, regardless of the outcome of $C2$, v returns the aggregated statistics, and u aggregates them on its local ones via summation. To avoid redundancy of the local statistics, if $u \in \mathcal{R}_v$, u subtracts its local statistics from the received ones before aggregating them. If $\neg C1 \wedge C2$ holds, v returns the aggregated statistics, and u substitutes its local matrices with the ones received from v . If $\neg C1 \wedge \neg C2$ holds, v reverts to the policy of PSC, and forwards $\hat{\mathbf{A}}, \hat{\mathbf{B}}$ to u . The updates of the local register \mathcal{R}_u are performed according to the aforementioned rules. With the negligible overhead of exchanging also registers, APSC allows leveraging partial aggregations and for completely asynchronous learning processes ($\hat{\mathbf{A}}, \hat{\mathbf{B}}$ are kept as in PSC). The convergence of APSC is lower and upper bounded by the ones of DSC and PSC, respectively.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT

Our experimental assessment aims towards realistic simulations of DFL scenarios, where we compare the proposed methodologies' efficiency and efficacy against ADMM.

A. Setup

Our setup consists of six benchmarks from the combinations of three *datasets* each peer (Section IV-A1), and a *network* defining the initial, logical communication topology among

peers (Section III-B). On each benchmark, we assess DIncFed with all the consensus mechanisms, in comparison with the work in [4] and two client-server baselines (Section IV-A2). We evaluate the methodologies by addressing efficacy and efficiency performance (Section IV-A4).

1) *Datasets*: We employed three datasets with increasing levels of realism: Heart Rate Analysis (HRA), Pneumonia MNIST (pMNIST) [20], Wearable Stress and Affect Detection (WESAD) [21].

HRA is a sequence of 42963 heart rate samples collected by a person's daily activities within six days, suitable for a next-step regression task. We chunked the dataset in subsequences of 300 timesteps. We produced peer-specific datasets by extracting 15 contiguous subsets of subsequences. The time series, ordered in terms of time, is divided into different portions one for each client. Then, we applied the standardization to each local dataset to have zero mean and unitary standard deviation. pMNIST contains 5856 pediatric chest X-ray images. The task is a binary-class classification of a lung with pneumonia (label 1) against normal (label 0). We scaled the 28×28 black-and-white images in the range $(0, 1)$. We divided the dataset into 15 peer-specific datasets. In our split, each peer can present either a 99%-1% or 1%-99% class imbalance.

WESAD contains 15 patient-specific sequences of 8 physiological measurements from wearable sensors. Each timestep of the sequences is labelled according to the expected cognitive state of the participant out of 4 possible states. We preprocessed data for each patient independently: we standardized the time series, and chunked it in subsequences of 350 timesteps. The peer-specific datasets correspond to the given patient-wise split of the original dataset.

To evaluate the capability of the algorithms to foster knowledge transfer and generalization among peers, we employed a *peer-wise* train-validation-test split. In particular, given the 15 peers of each benchmark, we employ a 9-3-3 split.

2) *Methodologies*: For each of the resulting 6 benchmarks, we tested 5 methodologies: ADMM with DAC as consensus mechanism, and DIncFed with the three consensus mechanisms (i.e., DSC, PSC, APSC). Additionally, for each dataset, we provided two client-server baselines. IncFed is the methodology proposed in [12], where the server collects the matrices A_c and B_c from all clients $c \in \{1, 2, \dots, C\}$, sums them and computes the Ridge Regression. Furthermore, we employ a slightly modified version of FedAvg, where the server collects the readouts from all clients (computed locally with the closed-form Ridge Regression) and averages them, weighting the contributions by the sizes of the local datasets. During the model selection, the hyperparameter space spanned across the underlying model and the methodologies. Regarding the ESNs number of reservoirs in $\{1, 2\}$, reservoir size of 100, leaking rate in $[0.1, 0.5]$, input scaling in $[0.7, 0.9]$, spectral radius in $[0.9, 1.2]$, input sparsity of 0.5, reservoir sparsity of 0.9, regularization of 0.001. Regarding the methodologies, we employed the same hyperparameter space as in [4] for ADMM; we set the number of consensus algorithm iterations of 4 for DIncFed with DSC, and 40 with PSC and APSC.

TABLE I

EFFICACY METRICS ON ALL THE BENCHMARKS. WE REPORT THE MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF NRMSE FOR HRA, AND ACCURACY FOR pMNIST AND WESAD. BEST RESULTS ARE HIGHLIGHTED IN BOLD.

GI	Method	HRA	pMNIST	WESAD
CS	FedAvg	0.122	74.52	78.89
	IncFed	0.123	86.06	82.09
RandR	DIncFed(DSC)	0.126±0.0010	85.51±0.7	81.17±0.6
	DIncFed(PSC)	0.124±0.0013	86.06±0.6	80.29±1.9
	DIncFed(APSC)	0.124±0.0006	86.20±0.4	81.92±0.6
	ADMM(DAC)	0.133±0.0091	50.04±12.5	57.39±7.3
NWS	DIncFed(DSC)	0.126±0.0011	88.53±0.6	79.57±1.3
	DIncFed(PSC)	0.124±0.0010	86.12±0.5	81.04±1.2
	DIncFed(APSC)	0.124±0.0010	86.02±0.3	82.12±0.8
	ADMM(DAC)	0.133±0.0091	50.04±12.5	57.39±7.3
BA	DIncFed(DSC)	0.126±0.0009	85.96±0.3	81.55±0.3
	DIncFed(PSC)	0.125±0.0014	86.07±0.4	81.40±1.4
	DIncFed(APSC)	0.124±0.0011	86.07±0.1	81.94±0.5
	ADMM(DAC)	0.133±0.0091	50.04±12.5	57.39±7.3

3) *Workflow*: For each benchmark and methodology, we conduct the corresponding experiment in two phases. First, in the *model selection* phase, where we determine the best hyperparameters configuration for the ESN and the learning algorithm. During the model selection, we train the models by using the 9 training peers, and we compute the metrics on the 3 validation peers. Then, in the *risk assessment*, we train the model by using both the 9 training peers and the 3 validation peers (for a total of 12 training peers), and assess the performance on the 3 test peers.

4) *Metrics*: We assess the algorithms with two groups of metrics, namely *efficacy* metrics and *efficiency* metrics. Efficacy metrics assess the performance of the resulting models in inference. We used Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE) on HRA and accuracy on pMNIST and WESAD. To evaluate how well peers transfer knowledge to each other and generalize over their local distribution, we calculate the metrics by averaging the performance of the readouts from training peers on the data from the validation/test peers (depending on the phase). Formally, given G training peers and E evaluation peers, the metric is computed as

$$p = \frac{1}{G} \sum_{g=1}^G \frac{1}{E} \sum_{e=1}^E p_{g,e} \quad (5)$$

where $p_{g,e}$ is the performance of model of training peer g run on the data of evaluation peer e .

Efficiency metrics assess the non-functional properties of the algorithms during the training phase. We provide: 1) the number of floating point numbers exchanged (FP); 2) the number of interactions between peers (Conn); 3) the wall clock time required to execute the algorithm (Time).

B. Performance results

In this Section, we analyze the results of the experiments on both the metrics groups.

1) *Efficacy*: On Table I, we report the efficacy metrics. Starting from HRA, we can observe that the resulting models of the training clients achieve a good generalization performance on the data from the test clients, regardless of

the learning approach used. In particular, the differences of NRMSE are negligible across the methods, and this is due to the rather small complexity of the dataset. However, deepening the observation on the consensus mechanism, it is evident that the fine-grained aggregation applied by PSC and APSC provides a small improvement in the performance and its consistency across the test peers.

The difference becomes evident with the extreme conditions of statistical heterogeneity of pMNIST already from the baselines: FedAvg fails to cope with the unbalance of the local data distributions. The same happens with ADMM, where the resulting models are not able to generalize on the test clients. Instead, we can see that the exact approach provided by DIncFed is robust to the statistical heterogeneity conditions simulated in this benchmark. Regarding the consensus mechanisms, we can see broadcast-based mechanisms fit best on the more realistic topologies. This can depend on how the nodes with the highest degree may be representative of the local distributions of the test peers. Finally, WESAD shows a consistent behavior with respect to pMNIST. DIncFed outperforms ADMM with all the network topologies while achieving performance comparable to the centralized baseline. In general, we can observe that ADMM fails to properly transfer knowledge whenever the task becomes more challenging. Instead, DIncFed proved robustness on the efficacy metrics on all the given benchmarks.

2) *Efficiency*: On Table II, we report the efficiency metrics. Here, we can observe that the results of the metrics are unrelated to the complexity of the dataset at hand. Instead, the FP metric is dependent on the hidden size and the output size of the ESN for DIncFed, and on the size of the readout for ADMM; the Conn metric depends on the overall communication policy described by the algorithm. We can observe that, on all the benchmarks, the metrics lean in favor of DIncFed. While the authors in [4] claim that transferring the self-correlation matrix B may not be feasible in low-resource environments, the empirical assessment proves that the iterative approach of ADMM requires the exchange of an amount of data which is orders of magnitude higher than DIncFed. This proves that, while the amount of data exchanged per interaction with ADMM is lower (the size of the readout is significantly smaller than the self-correlation matrix), the amount of data to exchange throughout the process is higher.

Furthermore, with DIncFed, we can enhance the granularity of the communications with APSC by allowing peers to filter out neighbors from whom they already received data. This is not feasible with ADMM due to the iterative nature of the learning process: while with DIncFed, we can easily determine whether we are receiving obsolete information, with ADMM making such a choice is not possible. The results lead to a better trade-off in terms of cost-per-iteration ratio.

C. Learning process analysis on WESAD

To better understand DIncFed with the different consensus mechanisms, we deepened our analysis on WESAD as it presents a real case of statistical heterogeneity (Figure 2).

TABLE II

EFFICIENCY METRICS ON ALL THE BENCHMARKS. FOR ALL THE METRICS, WE REPORT THE MEDIAN VALUE AMONG THE TRAINING PEERS. DINCFeD IS OUR MODEL. BEST PERFORMANCES ARE HIGHLIGHTED IN BOLD.

GI	Method	HRA			pMNIST			WESAD		
		FP	Conn	Time	FP	Conn	Time	FP	Conn	Time
CS	FedAvg	1200	12	5.4	2400	12	0.085	9600	12	27.05
	IncFed	61800	12	5.52	243600	12	0.123	65400	12	13.26
RandR	DIncFed(DSC)	41200	8	5.47	162400	8	0.133	43600	8	13.47
	DIncFed(PSC)	51500	81	5.52	203000	81	0.128	54500	81	15.31
	DIncFed(APSC)	30900	81	5.47	121800	81	0.129	32700	81	13.26
	ADMM(DAC)	9.60e+07	480000	149.4	9.60e+07	480000	143.41	7.68e+08	480000	194.07
NWS	DIncFed(DSC)	61800	8	5.38	243600	8	0.129	65400	8	13.28
	DIncFed(PSC)	51500	76	5.46	203000	76	0.128	54500	76	15.55
	DIncFed(APSC)	30900	76	5.6	121800	76	0.131	32700	76	13.47
	ADMM(DAC)	1.44e+08	480000	164.5	1.44e+08	480000	158.43	1.15e+09	480000	206.47
BA	DIncFed(DSC)	51500	8	5.62	203000	8	0.138	54500	8	13.27
	DIncFed(PSC)	51500	75	5.64	203000	75	0.134	54500	75	15.88
	DIncFed(APSC)	25750	75	5.69	101500	75	0.135	27250	75	13.58
	ADMM(DAC)	1.20e+08	480000	172.4	1.20e+08	480000	168.09	9.60e+08	480000	210.41

Fig. 2. Efficacy and efficiency along the learning process of DIncFed on WESAD.

Figure 2a reports the accuracy of the test data throughout the learning process. We can observe that combinations of communication topology and consensus mechanism exhibit different patterns in terms of accuracy development over time. In particular, the broadcast-based mechanisms converge within the first 5 interactions among the peers regardless of the underlying communication topology, with better stability in favor of the DSC consensus mechanism. The zig-zagging learning curve of each peer on the NWS topology happens due to the slight unbalance of the contributions caused by the inclusion of additional, random connections among peers. As expected, sampling-based consensus mechanisms tend towards a more stochastic behavior, with a slower convergence than the broadcast-based mechanisms. This is mitigated by the selection peers providing more relevant information with APSC, avoiding the redundancy to cause additional stochasticity in the

local learning process. Figure 2b reports the communication cost experienced by each peer throughout the learning process. These plots prove the advantages of employing peer sampling-based mechanisms since the amount of data transferred per connection is significantly lower than that of broadcast-based ones. This is beneficial for learning in low-resource environments: it allows avoiding network bottlenecks due to overflowing the network with data. Finally, we observe that this can be further mitigated with the use of APSC, since we allow the transfer of redundant information with respect to the one already aggregated.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The overarching objective of Decentralized Federated Learning (DFL) is to allow a set of peers to learn a model from local data and transfer local knowledge to others in a

federation, without the aid of a centralized entity, in an attempt to reach a global consensus. In the lower end of the cloud-edge continuum, this process must happen under restrictive hardware and communication constraints, where Echo State Networks (ESNs) proved their efficiency when dealing with tasks involving temporal data.

We proposed Decentralized Incremental Federated Learning (DIncFed), a DFL algorithm which leverages the efficient learning approach of ESNs to allow a federation of peers to reach an *exact*, decentralized consensus. This algorithm unfolds in two phases: a local learning phase, where each peer learns its local statistics, and a consensus phase. We proposed three consensus mechanisms, fitting the decomposition of Ridge Regression over the federation: Distributed Sum Consensus (DSC), where peers request and aggregate statistics from all neighbors in the communication topology; Peer Sampling-based Consensus (PSC), where peers sample a neighbor to interrogate, and dynamically update the communication topology to update the local neighborhood; Advanced Peer Sampling-based Consensus (APSC), which combines the best of both worlds, reducing the amount of data transferred by leveraging partial aggregations from neighbors. Our experiments aim to assess the quality of the models learned by the peers and the efficiency of the algorithm regarding the amount of data transferred to reach consensus, with varying initial communication topology and increasingly realistic datasets. In our experiments, we prove that DIncFed outperforms a competitor for DFL with ESNs on all the benchmarks, regardless of the consensus mechanism employed. Our methodology is robust and produces models with good generalization, even in cases of extreme statistical heterogeneity, without the need for bargaining with the amount of data exchanged. Furthermore, this behavior is further enhanced with the use of APSC, where the use of partial aggregations from other peers allows for faster convergence than PSC with fewer data exchanged throughout the process.

In future works, we plan to investigate several directions. First, we aim to distribute the algorithm in a realistic testbed, where peers are deployed in actual nodes of a distributed system and must for the existence of a *physical* communication topology. Second, we aim to include mechanisms for dealing with the varying availability of peers in federations where participants may join and leave the learning process as desired. Finally, we aim to enrich the sampling strategy in PSC and APSC with heuristics accounting for the statistical and system heterogeneity across the federation.

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